

THE UNIVERSITY OF
MELBOURNE

Deep Learning meets the Deep Sea: AI in microbial oceanography

Vini Salazar, Melbourne Bioinformatics
AI in the Life Sciences Webinar Series
July 2025

Why marine microbes?

- Comprise the majority of the biomass in the oceans (Abreu et al 2022)
- Critical roles in biogeochemical cycles
 - At least $\frac{1}{4}$ of Earth's primary productivity
 - Underpin global food networks

Earth's biological engine

The “microbial loop”: carbon is returned to higher trophic levels via its incorporation into bacterial biomass.

Seminal work by Larry Pomeroy (1974), Farooq Azam, Tom Fenchel, and colleagues (1980s).

Contrasts with the “classical” trophic network where:
phytoplankton → zooplankton → fish

plankton

noun [U]

/ 'plæŋk.tən/

“very small plants and animals that float on the surface of the sea and on which other sea animals feed”

– Cambridge English dictionary

Greek for “drifter”, or “wanderer”

Copepod of the order “Cyclopoida” (Burmeister, 1834).

Why AI? Why Now?

Microbial oceanography is *highly* interdisciplinary.

Diverse sources of data:

- Plankton images
- Molecular and genomic
- Satellite and remote sensing
- In situ environmental
- Weather and climate models
- Field surveys

AI helps us with scaling and integrating data analyses!

THE UNIVERSITY OF
MELBOURNE

AI for Plankton Image Classification

AI for Plankton Classification

Irison et al, Annual Review of Marine Science 2021

Commercial solutions for plankton imaging have existed for a few years (eg imbro's ZooSCAN[®]).

AI is rapidly improving our capability to scale data analysis.

>90% accuracy after removing rare classes (Luo *et al* 2018).

Human interaction is still

AI for Plankton Classification

CNNs are an ideal tool for image classification.

Pioneering work by Zheng & Wang (UCSD, 2015).

Challenges include:

- Data labeling
- Class imbalances
- Highly variable and/or low quality images

Errola et al, Artificial Intelligence Review 2024

Data Augmentation to the Rescue

THE UNIVERSITY OF
MELBOURNE

AI for Genome Reconstruction

Metagenomics

Environmental sample
(seawater)


```
Identifier —● @SRR566546.970 HWUSI-EAS1673_11067_FC7070M:4:1:2299:1109 length=50
Sequence —● TTGCCTGCCTATCATTTTAGTGCCTGTGAGGTGGAGATGTGAGGATCAGT
'+' sign —● +
Quality scores —● hhhhhhhhhghghghhhhhfhhhhfffffe'ee['X]b[d[ed'[Y[~Y
Identifier —● @SRR566546.971 HWUSI-EAS1673_11067_FC7070M:4:1:2374:1108 length=50
Sequence —● GATTTGTATGAAAGTATACAACTAAACTGCAGGTGGATCAGAGTAAGTC
'+' sign —● +
Quality scores —● hhhhgfhhcghghggfcffdhfehhhhcehdchhdhahehffffde'bVd
```

DNA sequence data

Genomes to reads and back again

	A	B	C	D	E	F
S1	1	3	5	1	3	5
S2	5	1	3	5	1	3
S3	3	5	1	3	5	1

Enter Variational Autoencoders

THE UNIVERSITY OF
MELBOURNE

Enter Variational Autoencoders

Better MAGs = better understanding of *genomic* and *functional* diversity in the oceans.

That Was Just a Sample (pun not intended)

THE UNIVERSITY OF
MELBOURNE

AI for Ocean Ecosystem Modelling

Ocean Forecasting and Microbial Ecology

nature

Article | [Open access](#) | Published: 04 December 2024

Probabilistic weather forecasting with machine learning

[Ilan Price](#)

Nature **637**, 84–90 (2025) | [Cite this article](#)

Model Integration is the Future

Machine Learning Predicts Biogeochemistry from Microbial Community Structure in a Complex Model System

Avishek Dutta,^a Thomas Goldman,^b Jeffrey Keating,^b Ellen Burke,^b Nicole Williamson,^b Reinhard Dirmeier,^b Jeff S. Bowman^{a,c}

FIG 2 Shift in average cell abundances across different phases in treated and nontreated columns. Shaded regions for generalized additive models (GAM) indicate ± 2 standard error.

Experimental setup:
A 148-day experiment to observe the microbial community shifts across different phases of sulfidogenesis and mitigation

Sample collection and processing

DNA sequencing and annotation

Preparing data for random forest modelling

Random Forest modelling

Predictive performance evaluation

Dependent variables

Independent variables

D ← **E**
Incorporating cell count data

Linear models for regression

F

		Actual			
		Class 1	Class 2	Class 3	Class 4
Predicted	Class 1	45	2	0	0
	Class 2	0	15	0	0
	Class 3	0	0	131	11
	Class 4	1	0	0	0

Confusion matrix for classification

Incorporation of the Microbial Loop

Levine et al, Annual Review of Earth and Planetary Sciences, 2025.

Challenges

Fennel et al, Nature Reviews Methods Primers, 2022.

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = physics + bgc_sms$$

Carbon flux

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = -\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla_3 C + \nabla_2 \cdot k_H \nabla_2 C + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(k_V \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} \right) + bgc_sms$$

Incorporation of ocean circulation

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = -uptake + remineralization$$

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = uptake - grazing$$

$$\frac{dZ}{dt} = grazing - excretion$$

$$\frac{dD}{dt} = excretion - remineralization$$

$$grazing = gZ \frac{P}{K_P}$$

$$grazing = gZ \frac{P}{P + K_P}$$

$$grazing = gZ \frac{P^2}{P^2 + K_P^2}$$

Modelling choices for parameterisation

Model resolution

The future?

CellVoyager: AI CompBio Agent Generates New Insights by Autonomously Analyzing Biological Data

Samuel Alber^{1,*}, Bowen Chen^{2,*}, Eric Sun^{2,3}, Alina Isakova⁴, Aaron J. Wilk⁵, James Zou^{1,2}

¹Department of Computer Science, Stanford University

²Department of Biomedical Data Science, Stanford University

³Department of Genetics, Stanford University

⁴The Phil and Penny Knight Initiative for Brain Resilience, Stanford University

⁵Department of Medicine, Stanford University

Abstract

Modern biology increasingly relies on complex, high dimensional datasets such as single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq). However, the richness of such data means that conventional analyses may only scratch its surface. Extracting meaningful insights from these datasets often requires advanced computational methods and domain expertise. Current AI agents for biology are primarily focused on executing user-specified commands and are therefore limited by the user's creativity and familiarity with which kinds of analyses are useful. Furthermore, these agents do not account for prior analyses already attempted by researchers, reducing their ability to build upon existing work. To address these limitations, we introduce CellVoyager, an AI agent that autonomously explores scRNA-seq datasets in novel directions conditioned on prior user-ran analyses. Built on large language models, CellVoyager ingests both the dataset and a record of prior analyses to generate and test new hypotheses within a Jupyter notebook environment. We evaluate CellVoyager on CellBench, a new benchmark based on 50 published scRNA-seq studies encompassing 483 analyses. Given only the background sections of these papers, CellVoyager outperformed GPT-4o and o3-mini by up to 20% in predicting which analyses the authors eventually conducted. We then carried out three in-depth case studies where CellVoyager is given previously published papers with their scRNA-seq datasets and conducts analyses to generate new findings. The original authors of each study evaluated these findings and consistently rated them as creative and sound; 80% of the agent's hypotheses were deemed scientifically interesting. For example, in one case study, the agent found that CD8⁺ T cells in COVID-19 infection are more primed for pyroptosis, which was not explored by the original researchers. CellVoyager also reanalyzed a brain aging dataset to discover a previously unreported association between increased transcriptional noise and aging in the subventricular zone of the brain. These results demonstrate that CellVoyager can act both autonomously and collaboratively to accelerate hypothesis generation and computational biology. It also highlights the potential of agents like CellVoyager to unlock new biological insights by reanalyzing the vast existing biological data at scale.

THE UNIVERSITY OF
MELBOURNE

Take-home message

AI can deliver so much information about marine life:

- Help make sense of complex data
- Scale analysis of large volumes of data
- Integrate data from different sources

Thank you!

Prof. Kim-Anh Lê Cao

Dr. Heroen Verbruggen

Dr. Vanessa R. Marcelino

Dr. Ben Goudey

Dr. Giorgia Mori

Bio-ORACLE team

 Lennert Tyberghein Flanders Marine Institute VLIZ Link	 Jorge Assis Centre of Marine Sciences Link	 Heroen Verbruggen University of Melbourne Link	 Samuel Bosch Agricultural and Fisheries Research Link
 Ester A. Serrão Center of Marine Sciences Link	 Olivier De Clerck Ghent University Link	 Salvador Fernández Flanders Marine Institute Link	 Lennert Schepers Flanders Marine Institute Link

Google Summer of Code

Melbourne Bioinformatics

BIOINFORMATICS + DATA SERVICES + INFRASTRUCTURE, FOR LIFE SCIENCES TODAY

THE UNIVERSITY OF
MELBOURNE

WARNING

This material has been reproduced and communicated to you by or on behalf of the University of Melbourne in accordance with section 113P of the *Copyright Act 1968 (Act)*.

The material in this communication may be subject to copyright under the Act.

Any further reproduction or communication of this material by you may be the subject of copyright protection under the Act.

Do not remove this notice